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NEST VISITS AND CHICK FEEDING BY YELKOUAN
SHEARWATERS *PUFFINUS YELKOUAN*
DURING THE CHICK REARING STAGE

SUMMARY

A total of 15 accessible nests of Yelkouan Shearwaters were regularly monitored at the largest breeding colony in Malta, and the arrival and departure time of each individual bird from these study nests were logged. Observations focusing primarily on the arrival and departure times, duration of time spent inside the nest and the amount of food presented to the chicks are presented.

Key words — Maltese Islands, duration of visits, feeding of chicks.

RIASSUNTO

L'autore ha controllato regolarmente nella maggiore colonia di Malta 15 nidi di Berta minore mediterranea, riportando l'ora di arrivo e di partenza di ciascun individuo, la durata del tempo trascorso dentro il nido e la quantità di cibo portato al pulcino.

Parole chiave — Berta minore mediterranea, Isole Maltesi, durata delle visite, alimentazione dei pulcini.

INTRODUCTION

The Yelkouan Shearwater *Puffinus yelkouan* colony at iRdum tal-Madonna, on the north-eastern side of Malta was discovered by ornithologists in 1969 and since then, it has been annually monitored by Birdlife Malta bird ringers (SULTANA *et al.*, 1975). Site visits intensified from 1982 to 2006 when this colony was incorporated within a nation-wide study of the breeding Procellariiformes (BORG *et al.*, 2010; SULTANA *et al.*, 2011). This back-

ground work served as the basis for four EU Life funded projects (*Life Yelkouan Shearwater Project* 2006-2010, *Life+ Malta Seabirds Project* 2011-2016 and *Life Arcipelagu Garnija* 2015-2020, *Pan Puffinus* 2021-2025). The breeding population at iRdum tal-Madonna was first estimated at around 250 pairs (Sultana *et al.*, 1975) but further investigations by the present author revealed that the colony was twice as large with an estimated 500 pairs (BORG & SULTANA, 2002; SULTANA *et al.*, 2011).

Yelkouan Shearwaters start to visit the breeding colonies in the early days of October with single birds remaining inside the nest during daytime (BORG & CACHIA ZAMMIT, 1986-87). By mid-November, night-time visits become more regular, and the courting birds can also be heard calling from inside the nest sometimes even during daylight (SULTANA *et al.*, 2011; *pers. obs.*). Egg laying starts around the last week of February and continues till the second week of March (GALEA, 1990-1991; SULTANA *et al.*, 2011). There is one instance of an egg laid in the first week of April in a predominantly Scopoli's Shearwater *Calonectris diomedea* colony along the north-western shores of Gozo, but the chick disappeared 3-4 weeks after hatching (SULTANA *et al.*, 2011; *pers. obs.*). The first chicks hatch in the third week of April (earliest being 17th) and the first fledging takes place in mid-June, but in the end of July a small number of nests would still be occupied by late chicks (SULTANA *et al.*, 2011).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Visits to the breeding colony at iRdum tal-Madonna were carried regularly (5-7 days per week) between the second week of October up to the first week of August from 2006 to 2010. Different areas holding accessible nesting sites were visited at intervals to reduce disturbance. For the purpose of this study carried out in 2007 and 2008, visits were intensified to seven days a week, focusing on one particular area located on the northern edge of the colony. Visits were carried out from sunset up to first light. The study area holds 15 pairs of Yelkouan shearwaters and every single bird occupying this site was ringed and re-captured on numerous occasions. Every bird was sexed and measured and where possible assigned to individual visible nests.

The first birds start egg laying towards the end of February (24-28th) and the last eggs are laid by the 15th of March (GALEA, 1990-1991; SULTANA *et al.*, 2011; *pers. obs.*). Incubation lasts 53 days (± 2 days) where both partners take turn to incubate the single egg. In general, it is the male who takes the first incubation spell which lasts from 8 to 11 days (average 9 days), later alternating with the female, and incubation spells decrease to 1-2 days closer to hatch-

ing. Hatching begins in mid-April and for the first 5 to 7 days the chick is accompanied by one of the parents during daytime. It is then left alone and visited at night to be fed by one or both parents.

Most of the nests are in deep and inaccessible areas among the boulder screes and inside deep narrow crevices. One small area situated on a wide ledge at the northern side of the colony holds 15 pairs. Nine nests are located deep inside narrow crevices and only six pairs are visible, nevertheless, it was possible to catch incoming and outgoing birds by placing oneself outside the nesting cavities waiting for the adult birds to arrive or depart from the colony. By repeatedly handling ringed adults over an extended period, it was possible to record the arrival and departure times to and from the colony as well as the time spent inside the nest by the adult breeding birds. On every visit during the chick rearing stage, it was also possible to measure the amount of food delivered to the chick by weighing the adult birds before entering the nest and again at their departure.

Although the area holds 15 nests and thirty adult birds have been ringed and subsequently re-trapped, sufficient data for the purpose of this study was collected from fourteen individual birds over the two-year period. This was because some of the adult birds were not re-trapped in 2007-2008 as they may have either died or had been on sabbatical (the reproductive stop year in procellariiforms). The arrival and departure time and incoming and outgoing weight of adult birds was recorded over the period of two years (2007 and 2008) during the chick rearing stage (April and June). When each of these adults subsequently emerged from the nest, they were caught again and re-weighed to calculate the amount of food fed to the chick during the time spent inside the nest.

RESULTS

Time of arrival and departure

The timing of arrival by birds at the colonies depends on several factors of which meteorological conditions as well lunar phases have the most natural influence. Artificial lights and sounds such as those emitted by boats at sea or from land-based sources near the colonies, also have a negative effect on the birds entering the nesting sites. Very little activity was noted during strong easterly winds (facing wind), and the six-day period around the full moon, very little activity was noted but activity was conspicuously evident during moonless nights and when the moon was covered by thick clouds during overcast nights. No calling birds and very little flying around the colony was noted dur-

Fig. 1 — Time of arrival and departure of adult birds from colonies after chick feeding visits.

ing the full moon. It was also noted that during very strong easterly winds, only breeding birds visit the colony, while non-breeding birds were ever present.

While visits to the colonies by non-breeding birds are conditioned by lunar and meteorological conditions, breeding birds, especially during the chick rearing stage, are not much perturbed by these two conditions as they continue to visit the nest albeit silently and without any lingering outside the colonies. This study showed that a small number of breeding birds arrive within two hours after darkness; most breeding birds were recorded entering the colonies at a later hour to feed their chicks. Six of these birds came into the colonies before 24.00 hours and 18 after midnight (Fig. 1).

The experienced adult breeding birds return to feed the chick almost daily, but usually every other day. First time breeders normally return every three days. Time spent inside the nest depended on the timing of visits by the adult birds, the first to visit the chick will spend the most time in the company of the chick. On the other hand, when the second parent arrives, the duration inside the nest is much less. Each time one of the parents arrived earlier than the partner to feed the chick, the second bird spent little time as possible with the chick and at least on three occasions, departed without feeding the chick. Out of the 24 birds logged, the minimum time spent with the chick was of one bird staying for 10 minutes, while the maximum time was that of 5 hours and six minutes. The average time spent with the chick was of two hours and fifty-seven minutes (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 — Time spent inside the nesting chamber in the company of the chick.

Amount of food delivered to chicks

Feeding visits by the parents are carried out almost daily with some individuals skipping a night, the latter are usually first-time breeders who have not mastered their timing. Old established breeders provide a meal to their chick each night up to around 7 to 12 days before fledging. Each adult bird was weighed as it was coming in and again as it was leaving the colony. This allowed the calculation of the amount of food delivered to the chick. Each food delivery varied in weight from as low as 5 up to 90grams (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 — Loss in weight in adult birds after every feeding session from 20th May to 30th June 2007-2008.

CONCLUSION

Further investigations on the relation between age, breeding experience and food delivery by the adult birds and the feeding frequency and the variety of food items presented to the shearwater chicks over a long period of time is recommended. This can provide a better picture of food presented to unfledged chicks in relation to their rate of growth.

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